

Synthesis of Quinazolone Substituted Amides and Piperazonium Salts of Quinazolone Substituted Acids as Possible Anticonvulsants

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Some amides and piperazonium salts of quinazolone substituted acids were prepared and screened for anticonvulsant activity against pentylenetetrazol induced seizures. Except two amides, the rest of the compounds showed lower protection than the corresponding acids.

LITERATURE survey on anticonvulsant drugs, reveals that certain dialkylmalonamides show significant activity with no discernible sedative hypnotic effects and the disubstituted cyanoacetamides are more active as anticonvulsants than malonamides¹. Alkylamides of glutamic acids², several piperazine derivatives³⁻⁵ and substituted quinazolones⁶⁻⁸ are also reported to have good anticonvulsant properties. Keeping these facts in mind a search for newer anticonvulsant compounds led us to synthesize (Scheme 1) some quinazolone substituted amides and piperazonium salts of quinazolone substituted acids.

Scheme 1

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected.

2-Phenyl-3-carboxy alkyl/aralkyl-quinazolin(3H)-4-one

6-Oxo-2-phenyl-4, 5-benzo-1, 3-oxazin (0.05 mole), prepared according to Sammour, Fahmy and Mahmoud⁹, and the appropriate amino acid (0.05 mole) were taken in pyridine (70 ml) + water (25 ml) and the reaction mixture refluxed for 5 hr. The major portion of pyridine was then distilled off and the residue digested with 200 ml of *N* HCl for 2 hr on a water-bath. The separated solid was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol. The compounds prepared are given in Table 1.

2-Phenyl-3-amido alkyl/aralkyl-quinazolin(3H)-4-ones

The amides (Table SI. Nos. 7-12) were prepared by following the general method of preparation and recrystallised from alcohol. All of them were characterized by their sharp melting points, analyses and the presence of bands for N—H (3100-3300 cm^{-1}),

$\text{N}-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-$ (1660 cm^{-1}) and $-\text{C}=\text{N}$ (1620-1630 cm^{-1}) in the infrared spectra.

Piperazine salts of quinazolone substituted acids

A mixture of (0.006 mole) quinazolone substituted acid in alcohol (10 ml) and piperazine hexahydrate (0.003 mole) was refluxed on water-bath for 15 min. The solid which separated out was filtered and dried. The compounds (SI. Nos. 13 to 18) were characterized by their sharp melting points, analyses and the presence of bands for N—H (3000-3150 cm^{-1}),

$\text{N}-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-$ (1660 cm^{-1}), $-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-\text{O}$ (1590-1610 cm^{-1}) and $-\text{C}=\text{N}$ (1620-1630 cm^{-1}) in the infrared spectra.

TABLE

Compound ^a	Y	M.P. °C	Mol. Formula ^b	ALD ₅₀ mg/kg	Seizures test Protec-24 hr % mortality	Pentyle'te- trazol Seizures test Protec-24 hr % mortality
1.	—CH ₂ —	174	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂	—	80	20
2.	—CH ₂ —CH ₂ —	162	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂	—	60	20
3.	$\begin{array}{c} \text{CH}_3 \\ \\ \text{—CH—} \\ \\ \text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2 \end{array}$	167	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂	—	0	100
4.	$\begin{array}{c} \text{—CH—} \\ \\ \text{CH}_2\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2 \end{array}$	171	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂	—	40	60
5.	$\begin{array}{c} \text{—CH—} \\ \\ \text{CH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5 \end{array}$	163	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂	—	60	40
6.	—CH—	234	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂	—	80	20
7.	—CH ₂ —	180	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂	400	20	80
8.	—CH ₂ —CH ₂ —	215	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂	800	40	80
9.	$\begin{array}{c} \text{CH}_3 \\ \\ \text{—CH—} \\ \\ \text{OH}(\text{CH}_3)_2 \end{array}$	129	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂	400	0	100
10.	$\begin{array}{c} \text{—CH—} \\ \\ \text{CH}_2\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2 \end{array}$	172	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂	>800	60	40
11.	$\begin{array}{c} \text{—CH—} \\ \\ \text{CH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5 \end{array}$	140	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂	>800	80	60
12.	—CH—	165	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂	>800	40	60
13.	—CH ₂ —	259	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₆	400	0	100
14.	—CH ₂ —CH ₂ —	262	C ₂₈ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₆	>800	20	80
15.	$\begin{array}{c} \text{CH}_3 \\ \\ \text{—CH—} \\ \\ \text{CH}(\text{OH}_3)_2 \end{array}$	260	C ₂₈ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₆	800	0	100
16.	$\begin{array}{c} \text{—CH—} \\ \\ \text{CH}_2\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2 \end{array}$	256	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₆	>800	40	80
17.	$\begin{array}{c} \text{—CH—} \\ \\ \text{CH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5 \end{array}$	261	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₆	>800	20	80
18.	—CH—	241	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₆	400	0	100

(a) The compounds 1-6 have recently been reported by us (*Indian J. Med. Res.* 1968, 67, 310).

(b) All the compounds were analysed for C, H and N and were found satisfactory.

Bioassay :

Approximate lethal dose determination : The method of Smith¹⁰ was followed for this study. Graded doses of the compounds were administered intraperitoneally in groups of two mice each. The dose of the compound killing one animal out of two was taken as its ALD₅₀.

Gross behavioural effects : Graded doses of the compounds were administered intraperitoneally in

groups of 5 mice each. After administration of a particular compound the animals were observed continuously for one hour for resultant behavioural effects, if any, like ataxia, loss of righting, pinnal and corneal reflexes, straub tail and analgesia in order to establish whether a particular compound had a stimulant effect or a depressant effect or no effect on the C.N.S.

Anticonvulsant activity : Anticonvulsant activity was determined by following the procedure of Parmar et al¹¹. A 5% aqueous suspension of gum acacia and the test compound was administered intraperitoneally at a dose of 100 mg/kg in groups of 5 mice each of either sex, weighing between 15-25 g. Pentylenetetrazol was injected subcutaneously at a dose of 80 mg/kg, 4 hr after the administration of the test compound and the mice were then kept under observation for 60 min. In the control group this dose of pentylenetetrazol caused convulsions in 100% animals within 60 min and 100% mortality within 24 hr. Transient intermittent jerks or tremulousness were not taken into account. Animals not exhibiting threshold convulsions during a period of 60 min after administration of pentylenetetrazol were considered protected. The number of animals protected in each group was recorded and the anticonvulsant activity of the compounds expressed as percentage protection. The mortality of these animals was recorded after 24 hr to obtain an idea about the ability of these compounds in protecting against pentylenetetrazol-induced death.

Results and Discussion

The compounds were found to have no significant effect in the gross behavioural studies. ALD₅₀ and anticonvulsant activity of the compounds have been recorded in the Table.

The table shows that the anticonvulsant activity of amides is generally lower than that of the corresponding acids except in the case of compounds 10 and 11.

The piperazonium salts (Sl. Nos, 13 to 18) showed less protection in comparison to the corresponding acids (Sl. Nos. 1 to 6) and amides (Sl. Nos. 7 to 12).

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